

**O'ZBEKISTONDA G'O'ZA O'SIMLIGIDA UCHRAYDIGAN EPIFIT
BAKTERIYALAR TASNIFI**

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada mikroorganizmlar, ularning ahamiyati haqida ma'lumot berib o'tilgan. Bundan tashqari O'zbekistonda g'o'za o'simligida uchraydigan epifit bakteriyalar, ularning qaysi oilaga mansubligi va o'sha oilaga mansub bo'lgan boshqa epifit bakteriyalar haqida ma'lumot berib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Mikroorganizmlar, epifit bakteriyalar, gramm negative bakteriyalar, *Pseudomonas sp*, *Enterobacter agglomerans*.

**КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ БАКТЕРИЙ-ЭПИФИТОВ, ОБНАРУЖЕННЫХ НА
ХЛОПЧАТНИКЕ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ**

Аннотация. В статье представлена информация о микроорганизмах и их значении. Кроме того, была дана информация об эпифитных бактериях, обнаруженных на хлопчатнике в Узбекистане, к какому семейству они относятся, и других эпифитных бактериях, принадлежащих к тому же семейству.

Ключевые слова: микроорганизмы, эпифитные бактерии, грамотрицательные бактерии, *Pseudomonas sp*, *Enterobacter agglomerans*.

**CLASSIFICATION OF EPIPHYTE BACTERIA FOUND IN COTTON PLANT IN
UZBEKISTAN**

Abstract. The article provides information about microorganisms and their importance. In addition, information was given about the epiphytic bacteria found in the cotton plant in Uzbekistan, which family they belong to, and other epiphytic bacteria belonging to the same family.

Key words: Microorganisms, epiphytic bacteria, gram negative bacteria, *Pseudomonas sp*, *Enterobacter agglomerans*.

KIRISH

Mikroorganizmlar hamma joyda uchraydi. Ular atrof-muhit omillari bilan ta'sirlashadilar va ozuqa moddalarining aylanishini tartibga solishda asosiy rol o'ynaydilar. Mikroorganizmlar azotni fiksatsiya qilish, fosfat eruvchanligi, uglerod, metan va oltingugurt almashinuvida muhim rol o'ynaydi va biogeokimyoviy siklni boshqaradi [1].

Epifitik bakteriyalar - bu o'simlik yuzasida parazit bo'lmagan holda barglar, ildizlar, gullar, kurtaklar, urular va mevalar kabi turli organlarda yashovchi bakteriyalardir. Hozirgi tadqiqotlarda epifitik bakteriyalar odatda o'simlikka zarar yetkazmasligi, ammo muz kristallari hosil bo'lishiga yordam berishi aniqlandi. Ba'zilar o'simlik o'sishiga yordam beradigan auksin gormonini ishlab chiqaradi va bakteriyalarning hayot aylanishida rol o'ynaydi.

Go'zada uchraydigan epifit bakteriyalarning aksariyat qismi GNB (gramm negative bakteriya) hisoblanadi. Barcha GNB orasida populyatsiyalarning ikkala tur epifitlar o'simlikning qarilik davriga qadar nisbatan barqaror bo'lgan tur bo'lib, *Pseudomonas sp*. o'simlikning turli

qismlarida (bargi, changi, tolasida) mavjud bo'lgan dominant tur ekanligi, *Enterobacter agglomerans* esa undan keyin ikkinchi o'rinda turadi.

METOD VA METODOLOGIYA

Pantoea agglomerans - grammusbat bakteriya, u *Erwiniaceae* oilasiga kiradi.

U ilgari *Enterobacter agglomerans* yoki *Erwinia herbicola* deb nomlangan va odatda o'simlik yuzalari, urug'lar, mevalar va hayvonlarda hamma muhitida uchraydigan hamma joyda tarqalgan bakteriya. [2]

1- rasm.1000 marta kattalashtirilgan *Pantoea agglomerans*

Pantoea agglomerans

Dunyo: Bakteriyalar

Bo'lim: Proteobakteria

Sinf: Gamma proteobakteriya

Turkum: Enterobakterales

Oila: Erwiniaceae

Tur: *Pantoea*

Sinonimlari:

Enterobacter agglomerans Ewing va Fife 1972

Bacillus agglomerans Beijerinck 1888

Erwinia herbicola (Löhnis 1911) Dye 1964

Bacterium herbicola Löhnis 1911

Bacterium herbicola Geilinger 1921

Pseudomonas herbicola (Geilinger 1921) de' Rossi 1927

Corynebacterium beticola Abdou 1969

Pseudomonas trifolii Huss

Pseudomonas - grammusbat, Gammaproteobakteriyalar turkumi, *Pseudomonadaceae* oilasiga mansub va 191 ta tavsiflangan turlarni o'z ichiga oladi. [3] Eng yaxshi o'rganilgan turlarga *P. aeruginosa*, *P. syringae*, tuproq bakteriyasi *P. putida* va o'simliklarning o'sishiga ko'mak beruvchi *P. floresanlar*, *P. lini*, *P. migulae* va *P. graminis*. [4] [5]

Ushbu organizmlar uchun yaratilgan umumiy nom *Pseudomonas*, 1894 va 1900 yillarda Valter Migula tomonidan noaniq ma'noda gram-manfiy, tayoqcha shaklidagi ba'zi sporulyatsion turlari bilan aniqlangan [6] [7].

2- rasm. Agar-agar muhitidagi *P. aeruginosa* koloniyasi

TADQIQOT NATIJASI VA MUHOKAMA

Genomika. 2000 yilda *Pseudomonas* turining to'liq genom ketma-ketligi aniqlandi; yaqinda boshqa shtammlarning ketma-ketligi aniqlandi, jumladan *P. aeruginosa* shtammlari PAO1 (2000), *P. putida* KT2440 (2002), *P. protegens* Pf-5 (2005), *P. syringae* pathovar pomidor DC3000 (2003), *P. syringae* pathovar ukol B728a (2005), *P. syringae* pathovar phaseolica 1448A (2005), *P. fluorescens* Pf0-1 va *P. entomophila* L48. [8]

2016 yilga kelib, *Pseudomonas*ning 400 dan ortiq shtammlari ketma-ketlikga keltirildi. [9] Yuzlab shtammlarning genamlari ketma-ketligi natijasida turkumda juda xilma-xil turlar aniqlandi. Darhaqiqat, *Pseudomonas*ning ko'plab genamlari o'zlarining genlarining atigi 50-60 foizini tashkil qiladi.

2020 yilga kelib Genlar bankda 500 dan ortiq to'liq *Pseudomonas* genamlari mavjud edi. Filogenomik tahlilda 494 ta to'liq proteom ishlatilib, barcha shtammlar bilan birgalikda ishlatiladigan 297 ta asosiy ortolog aniqlandi. [10] Ushbu genetik ortologlarning turkum darajasida metabolizm, tarjima va transkripsiyada ishtirok etgan oqsillar uchun boyitilgan va *Pseudomonas* yirik evolyutsion guruhlarida o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni aniqlash uchun butun naslning filogenom daraxtini yaratish uchun ishlatilgan. [10] Bundan tashqari, ko'pgina evolyutsion guruhlar uchun guruhga xos bo'lgan asosiy oqsillar aniqlandi, ya'ni ular ma'lum guruhning barcha a'zolarida mavjud edi, ammo boshqa *Pseudomonadalar*da yo'q edi. Xususiyatlari

Jins a'zolari quyidagi aniq xususiyatlarga ega: [11]

- novda shaklida
- Gram-manfiy
- harakatlanishni ta'minlovchi bir yoki bir nechta flagellum
- Aerobik
- Spora bo'lmagan shakllanish
- Katalaza musbat
- Oksidaza-musbat
- Bakteriologiya

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